

Reducing gender imbalance

SOME INTERESTING STRUCTURAL ACTIONS

Role models for female leadership: University of Belgrade

The University of Belgrade's School of Electrical Engineering recently appointed Assistant Professor Aleksandra Krstić Vice-Dean for Academic Affairs. In addition to the competence and capacity she will work to be a role model to inspire others.

Representation at the top: Munster Technological University

In January 2021, Professor Maggie Cusack was appointed the president of Munster Technological University in Ireland. Professor Cusack became the second woman ever to be appointed President of an Irish University and the first woman of a Technological University.

Supporting mobility for caregivers: National Research Council in Italy

The normal Short-Term Mobility (STM) programme in CNR supports research staff to spend a period of 21 days abroad. The GEP 2022-2024 includes a measure to integrate the STM with an additional budget to support applicants with care responsibilities, in the form of lump sum funding, so without the need to document.

Award "I include gender in research": University of Gdańsk

To promote gender-sensitive research, the MINDtheGEPs team at University of Gdańsk has instituted an annual award called *I include gender in research*. The prize is awarded the master and doctoral theses at the university from the last academic year that best include a gender perspective in their research.

Launching a participatory path: Jagiellonian University

Conducted by the Department of Security, Safety and Equal Treatment, participatory meetings with all members of the academic community were organised. Through *methods enhancing reflexivity and voice*, suggestions and consensus around key actions of the GEP were achieved. Additionally, an information campaign was carried out on the Facebook platform.

SOME INTERESTING CULTURAL ACTIONS

Lessons from the Open Forum: How to use male advocates and allies

The Advocates & Allies programme adapted by the THRIVE (*Towards Hiring, Resources, Inclusion, Value, and Excellence*) project at East Carolina University aims to change the institution's structures and processes by educating male privileged faculty members about equality and equity matters. At the MINDtheGEPs Open Forum on 14 December 2022, the Advocates & Allies programme was presented and discussed.

Developing a transformative mentoring programme: University of Turin

MINDtheGEPs joins forces with the Re-UNITA project at the University of Turin to develop a mentoring programme open to both men and women in early stages of their career and to women full professors. It offers career support through the deconstruction of the gender assumptions and underlying logic that govern hiring and promotion processes, the definition of academic excellence, and the general functioning of universities and departments. Combining one-to-one mentoring with peer mentoring and networking mentoring, and by stimulating reflexive paths both for mentors and mentees in a safe, mutual and confidential space that also involves men, it aims at being not only individually but institutionally 'transformative'.

Pioneers, researchers, leaders: Women of Gdańsk science

During the summer, prominent women in science from universities in the Daniel Fahrenheit Association in Gdańsk have been featured in the exhibition *Pioneers, researchers, leaders: Women of Gdańsk science*. The aim of the exhibition is to inspire more women to pursue careers in science, looking towards the future through a historical lens.

Empowering Women in Manufacturing: Mentoring at CTAG

In the framework of the cofounded project STRADA, CTAG (Automotive Technology Centre of Galicia) is developing a mentoring programme aiming at providing women in manufacturing environments with the necessary skills and awareness of gendered processes and structures to develop their professional careers, whether in academia or industry, rising to management and leadership positions.

